

METHOD OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE THINKING OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS BASED ON A COMPETITIVE APPROACH

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***Abstract.** In this article, the issues of development of students' creative thinking skills, the impact of creativity on human development and personality are highlighted, and the opinions and opinions of many scientists have taken place in this issue. The importance of ideational productivity in the development of creativity and proposals for the development of creativity are given.*

***Keywords:** creativity, thinking differently, thinking skills, creative strategy, creative approach.*

In his work titled “The New Uzbekistan Strategy” President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev emphasizes that the greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest legacy is good upbringing, and the greatest poverty is ignorance. Therefore, acquiring advanced knowledge, being truly enlightened, and becoming a person of high culture must become a continuous and essential need for all of us. The President's idea highlights the importance of turning youth into broad-minded, intellectual individuals as a primary goal.

Likewise, psychologist E.Goziyev points out that in scientific psychology, psychological factors are generalized into large bodies of materials, laws, and characteristics. Deep conclusions are drawn about a person's inner potential, talent, industriousness, and capabilities, describing them with universal human traits. As a result, it becomes possible to identify and predict human psychology, eliminate existing mental flaws, and prevent negative emotions. This, in turn, serves to intelligently describe the essence of social and socio-psychological relations.

A.R.Aripdjanova states that environmental factors influence an individual and their development of creative and innovative qualities. In turn, the creative process is defined by the unique characteristics of both the problem and the person themselves, shaping the nature of the product the person is striving to create.

Y.E. Shmeleva identifies the abilities and personal qualities that influence the formation and development of creativity, such as: divergence of thinking, originality of thought, semantic flexibility, the ability to identify and generate problems, the ability to produce multiple ideas, analytical skills, the ability to overcome stereotypes, and the ability to find numerous associations.

According to D.B.Bogoyavlenskaya, motivation can be either effective or passive. Representatives of this level of intellectual activity are strong and conscientious, yet they remain within the boundaries of initially discovered methods of action. Their activity lacks initiative and is always externally motivated.

Professor G.N.Ibragimova Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, emphasizes that a creative specialist must possess qualities such as ingenuity, self-criticism and critical thinking, adaptability,

independence, reasoning, courage and enthusiasm, perseverance in completing tasks, and goal orientation.

Sh.X.Pozilova considers creativity to be the activity directed at producing new, original ideas as a result of non-standard thinking by students. "Creative teaching" is described as a process of creative interaction between educator and learner or between learners via a specific medium, serving to develop the creativity of the individual.

Based on the creative level achieved through the process, we can combine tendencies and general abilities to develop the creative qualities of future pre-conscription military education instructors. This integration creates opportunities for adaptive alignment with the trajectory of increased creative activity.

Psychologist E.Goziyev identifies the criteria for developing students' creative qualities as motivational – namely, a value-based attitude towards professionally oriented activity. This includes a valuable motivational attitude towards learning military sciences, a desire to solve complex problems, the ability to collaborate with peers, and interest in professional growth.

Based on scientific research, the indicators of creative qualities development can be defined as: motivation, creative traits, and orientation towards the development of professional activity among future teachers. These include the ability to search for educational information from various sources, creative task execution, non-standard decision-making, swift adaptation to new conditions, solving simple problems in unique ways, and creatively reworking existing ideas.

It is well known that creative activity makes our daily life more engaging; science and art are unimaginable without creativity. Every time we express a complex thought or fill a blank page with text, we engage in creativity. If we can accomplish this effectively and in an extraordinary way, we may truly be called creative individuals.

Moreover, creative activity is one of the influential factors in our daily and professional lives. According to D.Sh.Jurayeva, the concept of creativity is conditionally defined as a feature that expresses original and novel development in artistic and practical activity through the psychological act of integrating, receiving, or combining different types of information in our consciousness.

M.M. Musurmonova explains that the development of creative qualities in individuals always requires the formation of knowledge, skills, and competencies in critical thinking.

The microelements of pedagogical activity consist of non-standard solutions. Even though pedagogical situations may seem similar at first glance, every action taken by the teacher in these situations is of great importance.

In the development of the creative qualities of future pre-conscription military education teachers, a key aspect is the simultaneous improvement of their critical thinking skills and creative thinking traits.

V.N.Drujinin's idea that "the development stage of highly creative individuals reflects adaptation to improve the balance of vital activity" is quite fitting.

Compliance with principles and criteria that define military education content with sensitivity to problems, selecting and systematizing military supplies using modern military approaches, and organizing military training materials all reflect proportionality in the development of creative qualities.

"Possessing non-standard thinking skills means being able to apply various educational methods relevant to the military education process and operate new types of military weapons and

technology." Furthermore, it includes the ability to navigate situations through creative thinking based on a creative approach in different military conditions.

From the above analysis, we can conclude that the creative process involves making necessary non-standard decisions, researching them, and, in some cases, abandoning them when appropriate.

Thus, during the analysis of elements of creativity within the didactic system, P.Y.Galperin and N.F.Talizina identified elements such as models of management, giving instructions, and achieving maximum development effect.

Y.E.Shmeleva asserts that students exhibit indicators of creative freedom through the general formation of work habits, broader dissemination of knowledge, adaptability, independent thinking, and undoubtedly necessary conditions.

E.A.Ponomaryov explains that the result of creative activity involves intuition and cannot be derived solely through logical conclusions. He associates creativity with two personal qualities: the motivation to explore during the thinking process and the intensity of sensitivity toward adjacent knowledge areas.

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